

**IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF LABOR
AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES**

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Abstract. *This article thoroughly analyzes the theoretical foundations of labor organization and management in industrial enterprises and their impact on economic efficiency. It is emphasized that effective labor organization allows for increased labor productivity, reduced production costs, and the rational use of human resources. The study presents broad and narrow approaches to labor organization, advanced management methods, as well as existing problems and recommendations for their elimination. The necessity of improving working conditions, labor standardization, monitoring, and increasing production efficiency through the introduction of advanced labor methods is substantiated. The research results are of practical importance in the formation of labor organization policy at enterprises.*

Keywords: *Labor organization, labor productivity, division of labor, cooperation, labor rationing, industrial enterprises, production efficiency, management, human resources.*

Introduction. In modern economic conditions, the successful development of industrial enterprises is determined not only by the level of their technical equipment and the progressiveness of the technologies used, but also by the organization of production and labor. Labor, as a factor of active production, has always been the focus of attention of both scientists and practitioners.

The successful operation of enterprises depends on the proper organization of labor. Creating favorable working conditions in production has been and remains one of the main priorities. The greatest value of the state is a person, that is, perfect conditions must be created in production for each specific employee. Labor organization is understood as a set of methods, measures, and forms of regulation of activities that ensure the development of the company. This concept includes labor discipline, workplace organization, and methods of stimulating labor activity. In the organization of labor, the wage system plays a key role. Therefore, wages are considered the main reason and incentive that connects a person with the means of production and productivity.

In this regard, the influence of the activities of industrial enterprises on the indicators of economic growth in our country is significant.

The development of industrial enterprises has a significant positive impact on economic development. Therefore, in today's era of renewal and implementation of new development strategies, the effective use of the capabilities of industrial enterprises, the continuous use of the achievements of scientific and technological progress, and the improvement of the use of labor resources are among the most important factors in the development of industrial enterprises.

"In recent years, comprehensive measures have been implemented in the republic to develop the textile, clothing, knitwear, leather and footwear, and fur industries of the light industry, expand the range and assortment of manufactured finished products, and comprehensively support the investment and export activities of industry enterprises"[1].

The rational and effective use of labor factors in the implementation of social labor relations is an important condition of modern economic development, and the scientific and innovative organization and management of labor is a constantly functioning factor of any activity. In any era and in all spheres of human activity, along with the level of equipment and technology, good, scientifically correctly organized labor has ensured the achievement of high results.

Literature analysis and methods. The economic content, theoretical and practical aspects of the concept of labor organization and management have been studied by foreign economists such as F. Taylor, F. Gilbreth, L. Gilbreth, K. Adametsky, A. Fayol, G. Emerson, G. Ford.

In the CIS countries, this concept is approached as utility, a material or spiritual good directed towards society and the individual. In particular, in the studies of Japan and China, unemployment and employment are defined as activities.

Scientific research on the statistical analysis of the state of employment and trends in the development of the human factor in Uzbekistan during the transition to the path of innovative development in our republic was conducted in the scientific works of K.Kh.Abdurakhmanov, Kh.P.Abulkasimov, P.Z.Khoshimov, O.E.Khayitov, I.A.Bakiyeva, M.M.Ziyaeva, N.Ulugmuradova, Kh.A.Mukhitdinov, N.M.Nabieva, and others.

Results. The basis of any activity, whether in production or in the service sector, is labor carried out purposefully over a certain period of time.

It is known that the production process is, first of all, a labor process, which includes the purposeful relationship between human labor, the object of labor, and the means of labor. Labor is the conscious activity of people aimed at a certain goal, as a result of which they create material goods and cultural values by changing existing things in nature and adapting them to their needs.

The essence of labor, expressed in this way, remains the basic condition of production in any human society. Because without labor, the creation of material goods, the production process, or the provision of services are impossible.

The object of labor is said to be everything in nature to which human labor is directed. The means by which people influence the object of their labor are called means of labor. Among the means of labor, tools of labor play an important role. The object of labor and the means of labor together constitute the means of production. However, no matter how modern, developed, and improved the means of production are, even if they fully meet the requirements of world standards, they do not move by themselves. They come into motion only after combining with labor power, that is, human labor capacity, the labor process takes place, material goods are produced, or certain services are provided. Therefore, in the labor process, that is, in the process of producing material goods or providing services, the direct labor of people plays an important role. Therefore, the rational organization and management of labor, its targeted use, prevention of wasteful expenditure of raw materials and material resources, and, on this basis, increasing the efficiency of production and service provision are among the most important and pressing problems in the current market economy.

Typically, labor is divided into two types: living labor and past labor (objectified labor). The object of labor organization and management is living labor. Therefore, this science deals with the issues of living labor.

Living labor is a physiological process in which people expend physical and mental energy. The different ratio of mental and physical energy expenditure has a decisive influence on the content of labor.

The complexity and diversity of the components of the labor process (methods and techniques), the possibilities of independent selection, calculation, design, and coordination of the order of their implementation, introduce significant changes to the content of labor. It should be noted that since the object of labor organization, standardization, and management is living labor, it should not be concluded that labor organization and management have no connection to past objectified labor.

On the contrary, they are very close and interconnected, since an increase in the rate of material labor input, for example, in one simple and real-life example, when the cutting depth of the equipment in the manufacture of a hoe handle is excessive, i.e., greater than or even deeper than indicated in the norm, leads to an increase in living labor input. In turn, as a result of an unjustified increase in the operating mode of equipment, the desire to reduce the consumption of additional living labor leads to premature breakdown of equipment, excessive wear, deterioration, or failure of equipment, i.e., increases the amount of materialized labor costs.

As market relations develop and competition intensifies, the forms of labor manifestation change (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Forms of Labor Manifestation.

If we pay attention to the content and essence of "Organization and Management of Labor," it ensures the fulfillment of such tasks as the organization of the content and methods, methods, forms of labor division and cooperation, observation and measurement of working conditions, time expenditures, and methods of labor standardization in order to ease, facilitate, and increase labor productivity.

When the term "labor organization" is applied to a specific enterprise, it can be interpreted broadly and narrowly. In a broad sense, it refers to all issues related to the organization of labor, production, and management. Supporters of this interpretation approach the organization of labor activity at the enterprise as a whole. According to other authors, although such an understanding of the content of the concept of "labor organization" is correct from the point of view of the social significance of the corresponding phenomenon, due to the presence of living labor in the production process at enterprises, it makes it difficult to study it fully and comprehensively.

In a narrow sense, labor organization is understood as a set of practical measures, such as the organization of live labor, division and cooperation of labor, organization of workplaces, rationalization of methods, conditions, and rest schedules, labor

standardization, training and advanced training of employees, material incentives, and strengthening labor discipline.

Discussion. Based on our research, we can emphasize that the organization of effective labor activity (requires the presence of objects and means of labor):

- organization of working conditions (requires technological and environmental factors); organization of labor relations (requires the formation of relationships between employees);
- organization of labor remuneration, labor measurement, standardization, and assessment of labor costs based on its quality.

The solution of these problems, in addition to having independent significance, is also considered as an integral function of the organization of labor activity.

In order to create comprehensive conditions ensuring the most effective labor activity of employees at enterprises, it also sets itself the systematic implementation of such tasks as the study, improvement of labor, and the development of the theory and practice of establishing comprehensively substantiated labor norms, as well as the search for opportunities to increase labor productivity based on the effective use of working time.

It should be especially noted that factors that slow down and stop the increase in labor productivity still exist in the current conditions of a market economy. Because enterprises producing products and providing services achieve planned income (profit) not by continuously reducing production costs and increasing the volume of manufactured products, but by using the shortage and scarcity of their products or services and increasing their prices. This situation, in turn, not only intensifies the further development of the uncontrolled inflationary process, but also prevents the widespread introduction of comprehensively scientifically based labor norms and reduces the costs of production, organization, and management of the production process.

Including a set of issues related to the organization of labor, monitoring, verification, analysis, calculation, implementation of labor performance, organizational and technical work, the content of which is determined by:

- development of technical, technological, and production organization processes at enterprises;
- improvement of the division of labor and cooperation in connection with the growth of the cultural and technical level of employees;
- placement of executors and determination of the most appropriate ways of using working time for the positive solution of these tasks;

- selection of the most effective forms of work in the aggregate and at the workplace and job substitution, clear definition of the duties, rights, and responsibilities of each member of the production team;
- organization of workplaces and provision of the performer with tools and equipment corresponding to their physiological and anthropometric character and aesthetic perception, continuous improvement of workplace service, introduction of the most effective service procedures that eliminate waste of working time;
- improvement of the labor process, introduction of advanced methods and techniques of labor, achieving this by designing and implementing the most rational labor process that ensures high labor productivity of employees, as well as identifying, studying, selecting and disseminating advanced methods and techniques of labor;
- organization of personnel selection, training, advanced training, improvement of work forms in this process.

Conclusion. For the effective implementation of labor organization and management, the workers, specialists, and managers of all economic entities face a single goal: to ensure the targeted, systematic, and rational use of existing opportunities and resources in today's world, where the shortage of resources is becoming increasingly noticeable.

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